

CONSISTENCY AND RELEVANCE OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation

In this article we will focus on the scouting and dolrzabism of English Language Teaching. The role of teachers in the teaching of English, the participation of students, the opportunities created for the increase in language skills are all – about all.

Key words: English Language Teaching, qualified teachers, learners, pedagogical technologies, thesis, games, manuals.

Introduction.

Today, many opportunities are being created for students to acquire knowledge. These are in a sentence, qualified teachers, modern pedagogical technologies, equipped schools, educational courses all this is for young people who are the future of our country. The scarcity, urgency of training is increasing. Now we have a topic-we'll talk about teaching English – English is the language of the people's Republic of China. Therefore, if we delve into this knowledge, we can communicate and find our way, even in any land, reach our goal. Therefore, the importance of teaching English language is increasing. All attention is paid to this process. In order to improve the skills of teachers, education abroad, qualification courses, for the sake of growth, the reader is organizing shifts - trainings, methodical evenings for obtaining only knowledge. Various innovative pedagogical technologies (methods, games, theses, technological tools, manuals) are being created. In the premises of the school (school, educational center, institute, University, College, Academic Lyceum, private school), all conditions are created for students ' education. Getting only knowledge from the readers is no more than what was left of doing. One of the most important tasks of the present time is the formation of English language knowledge in students. the English language is becoming more and more consistent and relevant. In the organization of this, many laws came into force. In accordance with the resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2021 № PP – 45117 "on measures to bring the activities of popularization of foreign language learning to a qualitatively new level", as well as for the effective

implementation of organizational measures on popularization of teaching English, the Cabinet of Ministers decides: To establish such a procedure, in accordance with which the agency: coordinates the activities of state bodies and organizations, local executive authorities and state educational institutions in the field of popularization of Foreign Language Teaching; establishes contacts with foreign and local partners and organizes their financial, organizational and methodological support to attract the popularization of foreign language learning in the country; together with the ministries and departments, it develops and implements methodologies that give the opportunity to carry out professional activities of civil servants in foreign languages; establishes measures to popularize the study of at least ten foreign languages with high demand; develops qualification requirements and evaluation criteria for Foreign Language teachers, and organizes the process of granting them the qualification category on the; Control of the quality of Education under the Cabinet of ministers together with the state election confirms the list of internationally recognized certificates assessing the level of knowledge of foreign languages, as well as the conformity between the levels of national and internationally recognized certificates determining the level of knowledge of foreign languages. As you can see, if the creation of such an info project increases the number of English speakers, it will not come down. To approve the proposal of the Ministry of Higher and secondary special education of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the termination of the activities of the Republican scientific-practical Center for the development of innovative methods of teaching foreign languages under the State University of World Languages of Uzbekistan (in subsequent places — the Center). The agency is the legal successor of the Center for the development and permanent improvement of state educational standards, educational plans and programs, educational and methodical manuals in accordance with international standards for foreign languages for the entire system of continuing education, rights and obligations, as well as economic agreements; On the basis of the four staff units of the center, in cooperation with the prestigious training centers of foreign languages of foreign countries, a network qualification improvement structure on the system of bilateral certification is organized; territorial representation of the agency is financed from the account of state budget funds, organizational and logistical provision of their activities is carried out by the Council. The following are the sources of funding for the activities of the agency: funds envisaged to be allocated in 2021 from the state budget to the Ministry of Higher and secondary special education of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the

professional development of teachers; funds of the state budget; funds of international financial institutions and financial organizations of foreign governments, grants; sponsorship.

Straight up, it requires a lot of funds for the work to be done there. But among our people there is statement an impenetrable action called zero, it is not surprising. As we blow such diarrhea, we have our own representatives, we do it with the help of these are, of course.

5. To organize mobile groups (in subsequent places — mobile groups) for the qualification of Foreign Language teachers of educational organizations under the agency. In this case, the following is implied: the involvement of mobile groups primarily in the professional development of teachers of educational organizations located in remote areas or with low level of education in foreign languages; the formation of mobile groups in the composition of non-governmental educational organizations and representatives of foreign partners operating in the Republic and financing of their activities from the account of agency, Ministry of public education and non-budgetary funds of the Ministry of Higher and secondary special education, grants and other sources not prohibited by legislation; on the basis of the principle of “Cascade” mobile groups provide methodological and organizational assistance to the training and popularization of foreign language trainers (coach) among experienced foreign language teachers in the regions and to the organization of their activities for the professional development of teachers of foreign languages in the region. The agency together with the Ministry of public education of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Higher and secondary special education shall establish mobile groups starting from the 2021/2022 academic year. In this, the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the authorities of the regions and the cities of Tashkent, in agreement with the agency for the organization of the educational process on the ground for mobile groups on a permanent basis, shall ensure the reimbursement of all costs associated with the exploitation of vehicles (micro-buses).

Here it is told about the principle of “Cascade”. Such principles will enhance our mission . You can not say, exchange ideas with top-class teachers from us, get knowledge from trainers. It is a method of finding answers to our difficult questions. The following: the list of general secondary educational institutions, on the basis of which specialized schools for teaching foreign languages are established, as well as the higher educational institutions attached to them, shall be approved in accordance with Annex 1; in 2021, the program of equipping

specialized schools for teaching foreign languages with technical means shall be approved in accordance with Annex 2. In this: equip schools with technical means specified in Annex 2 of this decree from the account of the local budget and its additional sources; higher educational institutions attached to specialized schools for teaching foreign languages should be established as the base higher educational institution for teaching foreign languages, and territorial representations of the agency should be placed in them. The following are the main directions of the activities of specialized schools for the teaching of foreign languages: creating conditions for the development of basic language skills (listening, reading, writing and speaking) of students, including the organization of in-depth study of foreign languages by combining foreign languages in higher educational institutions; introduction of internationally recognized methods of teaching and assessing students in foreign languages and their knowledge, including wide application of distance and other modern forms of education in the educational process, as well as teaching other subjects in foreign languages; ensuring that students 'worldview, potential increase and increase their competitiveness in the labor market through at least two foreign languages' perfect assimilation. Such conditions, which are prepared for our readers, inspire the teacher himself, motivate them to further develop their knowledge and skills, we can not be mistaken. The following are the main tasks of higher education institutions attached to specialized schools for teaching foreign languages: methodological support of the educational process, assistance in strengthening and applying the basic language skills of students, including the involvement of foreign specialists in the educational process; taking measures to attract qualified professors, teachers and talented students to the educational process, as well as organizing master classes; establishing courses and clubs for teaching foreign languages, as well as organizing competitions and Olympiads among students. The expenses of higher education institutions attached to specialized schools for the popularization of Foreign Language Teaching in specialized schools should be covered from the account of extra-budgetary funds of these organizations. The following requirements are set for the level of foreign language acquisition for teachers of foreign languages of state educational institutions: starting from 2022/2023 academic year, applicants newly admitted to the positions of teachers of foreign languages of state educational institutions must have at least a national B2 level or an international certificate of equivalent level; Up to the 2022/2023 academic year, all teachers of foreign languages operating in state higher education institutions must have

an international certificate of at least S1 level national or equivalent level; up to the 2024/2025 academic year, 50 percent of teachers of professional Sciences (except foreign language) operating in state higher education institutions must have an international certificate of; Up to the 2024/2025 academic year, all foreign language teachers operating in general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions must have at least B2 level of national or equivalent level of international certificate. The state committee for quality control of Education under the Cabinet of ministers together with the Ministry of public education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Higher and secondary special education and the agency shall organize training of teachers of educational organizations for obtaining the appropriate certificate within a month. An increase in the interest in obtaining international certificates is also caused by the 50 percent exemption from certification. Such levels of qualified teachers themselves are no longer useful and preferable. In fact, certificates of this type are of the same interest in all teachers. There are a lot of different certificates such as international, National Certificate, APTIS, IELTS. So there are also many opportunities to get them. The following: in accordance with Annex 3 of the program of measures to improve the quality of teaching foreign languages, to expand the scope of scientific research, to increase the population's interest in the study of foreign languages; target indicators for improving the system of teaching foreign languages in the educational system should be approved in accordance with Annex 4. The heads of ministries and departments, the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent City authorities shall determine that they are personally responsible for the timely and qualitative implementation of the tasks set forth in the program of measures complex, as well as for the targeted indicators on improving the system of teaching foreign languages. It is necessary to establish such a procedure, according to which: a) the procedure for assessing 4 skills (listening, understanding, reading, writing and speaking) of participants in the Republican Olympiads conducted in foreign languages is introduced. Ensure that the Ministry of Education, together with the agency, will conduct the Republican stage of Olympiads in foreign languages on the basis of an improved procedure starting from the 2021/2022 academic year, as well as attract specialists of international organizations that conduct examinations on private and foreign, including foreign languages, operating on the jury; b) starting from the 2022/2023 academic year, a special test procedure is established to determine the level of knowledge of foreign languages of the selected secondary schools,

starting from the 2024/2025 academic year. Let the Ministry of Education consider measures to improve the methodology of teaching foreign languages on the basis of the results of special tests conducted jointly with the agency and the state agency for quality control of Education. Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and Tashkent City in order to improve the quality of teaching foreign languages in their regions: annually allocate not less than 1 billion sums from the local budget to provide schools in the district (city) with the necessary literature, equipment and modern information technologies for teaching foreign languages; Together with the agency and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, work is underway to attract qualified foreign specialists who have a language in general education institutions, including reimbursement of costs associated with their involvement and placement shall be carried out from the account of local budget funds; Together with the agency held an open competition in each district (city) and set up a system of sending at least two English teachers and one other foreign language teacher from the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent to improve their short-term skills in foreign countries.

If you go to foreign countries and you know how much the language is dying, then at the moment this is also easy. Recently, our robbers went to England and began to improve their qualifications. They are friends with the methods they have learned from us. Do not see the enthusiasm, enthusiasm in them, pass a lesson with a passing interest and enthusiasm, a person who does not know how a penny has passed.

In order to digitize the teaching of foreign languages, to introduce modern information and communication technologies into the Sphere: a) to set up online courses for teaching young people to foreign languages at IT centers in the regions, and to cover part of these costs from the account of the Youth Fund in accordance with the established procedure in the legislation. The Ministry of development of Information Technologies and communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall approve a plan of measures for the organization of online training courses involving foreign specialists in IT centers within two months; b) simplify the procedure for licensing the activities of educational organizations that make up the educational process on the basis of distance (online) technologies of teaching, provided that: having revised the conditions of the educational organization on the basis of educational means, establishing separate requirements for distance (online) technologies of teaching; forming the legal framework for the organization of the educational process on the; to

take into account the possibility of carrying out the educational process in a remote (online) way through automated programs and video courses; to create an opportunity to attract to the educational process some areas, including pedagogical personnel in the direction of information and communication technologies, as well as individuals with practical skills. The state committee for quality control of Education under the Cabinet of ministers, the ministry for the development of Information Technologies and communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Justice shall submit within two months a draft decision on the revision of licensing procedures for the activities of educational organizations established on the basis of distance (online) technologies of The Ministry of Higher and secondary special education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the bodies of Public Administration, which are institutions of Higher Education under its jurisdiction, should take measures to establish centers (courses) of teaching foreign languages to teachers and students on the basis of Public-Private Partnership in higher education institutions until the end of 2021.

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